

Pathology of Explanted Transvaginal Meshes

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Abstract : The use of polypropylene mesh devices for Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) spread rapidly during the last decade, yet our knowledge of the mesh-tissue interaction is far from complete. We aimed to perform a thorough pathological examination of explanted POP meshes and describe findings that may explain mechanisms of complications resulting in product excision. We report a spectrum of important findings, including nerve ingrowth, mesh deformation, involvement of detrusor muscle with neural ganglia, and polypropylene degradation. Analysis of these findings may improve and guide future treatment strategies.

Keywords : transvaginal, mesh, nerves, polypropylene degradation

Conference Title : ICOG 2014 : International Conference on Obstetrics and Gynaecology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : September 26-27, 2014